

A STUDY ON BEHAVIORAL FINANCE OF INVESTORS IN BANKS

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The article looks into the implications of financial behaviour and how it affects an investor's choice of investments.

Design/ Methodology: The study's information collected from secondary sources like magazines, books, and journal papers that were found using search engines like Google Scholar, Researchgate, and others.

Findings/ Results: According to the results of this study, investor perceptions unquestionably have a strong and significant impact on financial decisions. In order to choose the best investment products, the behavioural finance framework looks into the attributes of investors' behaviour. Investors should diversify their investments to connect to the lowest risk.

Originality Value: Every investor needs to choose their investments wisely. Therefore, although some investors do not do so, it is the investor's responsibility to follow the information provided by the bank. According to the study, it will be helpful to identify the factors influencing investors' investment decisions by conducting a behavioural survey.

Paper Type: Case Study

Keywords: Behavioral Finance, Banks, Psychological Factors, SWOT Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

As per the traditional view of finance, investors always focus on risk-return factors rationally and ignore psychological factors. Recognizing psychological factors in financial decision-making gradually gave birth to a new area of financial research. This new field of study is called "behavioural finance" [1]. Financial behaviour considers how various psychological attributes impact investors' ability to make their investment decisions. It attempts to bridge the gap between actual behavior and expected behavior [2]. It is a relatively new school of ideas that explores the impact of the psychological nature of financial practitioners [3]. Studies show some behavioral finance theory identifies psychological phenomena of investors which furthermore analysis customers attention on the key factors such as economic growth, interest rate and also the per-capita income. Past research indicates banks takes predominant step to decrease risk under the economic fluctuations and increase the attraction of resource by paying the facilities and credits [4]. However, some stream of literature focuses on behavioral biases which have an impact on the investment decision making process. It explains how emotions and cognitive errors influence the decision making process of investors. More likely, some studies explains about human behaviour with investment decisions which help to understand market anomalies and the inconsistencies that challenge the decision making theories. Further, research demonstrated behaviour of the human being is the potential and expressed capacity for mental, physical and social activity in various phases of life [5]. Nevertheless, studies portrays behaviour factors in risk management process may improve the efficiency and thereby contribute not only to success of the banks but also improve the welfare of the society at large. Research shed insight on manager's decisions, which are imperative under overwhelming risk settings [6].

The financial decision making process provides better understanding to the investors about risks and the opportunities involved in the investment. Moreover, a well-planned action of resources allocation leads to highest possible return on investment. Furthermore, investors focus on short and long term investment, which are further categorized into capital investment, strategic investment, modernization etc. Eventually all the major decision are made based on the two parameters risk and returns [7]. Studies proposes of the investment decisions made in the stock market is based on market outcomes. Evidence is also influenced by psychology

and demotions, which are more convincing and receiving greater acceptance and on the contrary finance area is reluctant to admit the view of psychologists who proposed this model [8].

II. RELATED RESEARCH WORK

Studies suggest that investment is made by customers due to their rational behaviour where they examine the risk associate with investment and invest to gain maximum gains. The study is taken from search engines such as Google Scholar and ResearchGate from the year 2011-2021 and the keywords are Behavioral Finance, Investment Decisions, Market Efficiency, and Developments.

Table 1: Exhibits the behavioral finance of investors in developmental banks

S. No	Focus/Area	Contribution	References
1	Highlights on the development of behavioural finance.	The study analyzed the combination of conventional theories and behavioral theories that should be considered to make better investment decisions regarding finance.	Joo & Durri, (2015). [2]
2	Development of business finance based on financial history.	The research focused on the importance of the study and its central place in creating a connection between real-life situations and traditional theories.	Kapoor & Prasad, (2017). [3]
3	Behavioural finance influence on investment choices	According to the studies and findings, behavioural finance significantly affects investment choices. This study was able to offer credible evidence that investors' decision-making is frequently influenced by heuristics and prospects.	Ogunlusi, & Obademi, (2021). [9]
4	Systematic analyses and an overview of behavioral finance.	The study focuses on several personal and institutional investors who have a considerable influence on financial behaviour. With the advanced improvement of financial markets all around the world, more and more academics are getting involved in financial behaviour research.	Huang, et al., (2016). [10]
5	Measures of financial knowledge of the respondents.	As more people participate in the financial markets, the emergence of new investment products and services has accompanied or even encouraged market activity.	Rooij et al., (2011). [11]
6	Highlights investor behaviour, but also looks at how decisions concerning savings and investments are made.	Financial decisions in India are not taken seriously and lack adequate planning for long-term finance. They are considered based on perception, word of mouth, past returns, and other factors.	Kandpal & Mehrotra, (2018). [12]
7	Unexpected and sudden economic movements have been either directly or indirectly influencing stock returns.	This study concentrated on the average pricing method and capital structure as two factors that affect investment choices.	Kadariya, (2012). [13]
8	Focuses on gaps and how these can be	Theories that support the efficient market hypothesis (EMH) are divided into three sections: studies that	Sharma, & Kumar, (2019). [14]

	simplified, for behavioral finance to be widely accepted as a conventional alternative approach to EMH.	provide stock market evidence that the EMH has failed, behavioural finance studies that discuss investor behavioural biases separately while considering their impact on stock prices, and empirical research on the impact of investor confidence on stock prices.	
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From the above literature, it is observed that the majority of researchers have focused on fundamental concepts of behavioral finance and they have not made an attempt to explore the behavioral finance aspects in the context of the banking sector. Hence, the present study is intended to focus on analyzing the behavioral finance aspects in the banking sector.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- (1) To study the concept of behavioral finance.
- (2) To guide the investors about the various investment opportunities in the banking sector.
- (3) To determine the risk and return of the investors in banks products.
- (4) To study the SWOT analysis of the financial behavior of the investors in banks.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Secondary sources of data were used in the research study. Research publications, journals, magazines, and books are some of the informational sources used in this article. The financial behaviour of bank investors was reviewed using a SWOT analysis.

V. BEHAVIOURAL FINANCE CONCEPT

The study of investor psychology and how it affects investment choices is known as behavioural finance. This field lightens the rationality assumption found in traditional finance theories and clarifies how psychological biases affect actual investors [3]. Additionally, researchers have found that investors maintain well-diversified portfolios and trade sparingly in order to minimise taxes and other investment costs. In practice, investors behave in a variety of ways. They trade frequently and have peculiar stock selection ability, leading to unnecessary investment costs and return losses, which led them to understand the concept of behavioural finance [15].

Behavioral factors are important in the decision-taking process of investors. As a result, investors must take the necessary steps to reduce or avoid illusions such as overconfidence, representativeness, anchoring, and self-control for influencing their decision-making process, particularly investment decisions [16].

VI. VARIOUS INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITIES IN THE BANKING SECTOR

6.1 Tax-Sheltered Saving Schemes:

For individual income tax assesseees, various tax-saving solutions are regularly made accessible. These programmes offer a variety of features, including the potential for tax benefits, liquidity, safety, risk coverage, old age benefits, etc., that may encourage and persuade investors to participate [17].

(1) Employee Provident Fund Scheme:

The Government of India established the Employees' Provident Fund Organization (EPFO) to provide financial and social security to industrial workers and their dependents. The results of the study, monthly salary is the most important factor influencing employees' perceptions of the current status of EPF investments, barriers to EPF investment, and future EPF corrective actions [18].

(2) Public Provident Fund Scheme (PPF):

Among all investment opportunities in India, Public Provident Fund is one of the most secure long-term investment options. PPF continues to be a great tax-saving and investment platform for many investors. A PPF account can be opened at a bank or post office. This scheme fulfils the requirements and desires of investors who want to keep their earnings for a longer period of time and who do not want any price movements in their risk frame [19].

(3) Mutual Fund:

A mutual fund is a trust that deposits money from investors by selling shares of the fund to the public in the same way that any other type of company does. The funds raised are invested in various avenues such as stocks, bonds, money markets, and commodities. As such, each mutual fund invests money to achieve specific investment goals, which is shared by all of them. A qualified fund manager is in charge of carrying out a fund's finance strategy and overseeing its portfolio trading operations [20].

(4) National Savings Certificate:

Anyone seeking a secure investment opportunity to earn a consistent return while saving taxes can invest in NSC. NSC provides interest guarantees as well as complete capital protection. In contrast to many fixed income schemes, they are unable to provide inflation-beating earnings like tax-saving mutual funds and the National Pension System. Prospective investors can now easily access NSC because it is now available in banks across the nation, thanks to the government [21].

(5) Life Insurance:

Banks have started aggressively selling financial products to their customers as insurance policies as a result of the growing financialization of the economy. The practice of banks selling complicated life insurance products to their customers, especially the unwary ones who have some money and are looking to keep it in a low-risk instrument, is analysed in the article. The customer is presented with an investment product by the relationship manager that also includes life insurance [22].

6.2 Marketable Instruments:

Investment in the market is no longer a passive repository for extra liquidity. Instead, general investment and investment motivated by liabilities are linked to market investment [23]. Managers can identify their efficient divisions and inefficient divisions of Investment avenues by comparing each division's efficiency to that of any other banks. After a study revealed that its marketable securities investment division's efficiency was below average when compared to other financial institutions, the bank realised it had to boost this division's efficiency [24].

Study results hold provided that the connection between banking and securities activities was strengthened as a result of developments in the financial market, such as securitization, institutionalisation of investment, and the emergence of complex financial instruments. However, because of their special function as a source of liquidity, banks' stability continues to be essential for the stability of the entire financial system [25].

6.3 Deposits:

Deposits leave the banking system as spreads on deposits are widened by banks. In concentrated markets, deposit spreads rise more and deposits flow out more, which is consistent with the market power mechanism. Deposits, which are the primary source of liquid assets for households, have a strong relationship with the liquidity premium. Bank lending is impacted by the deposits channel because deposits are a particularly reliable means of funding for banks [26].

Deposits, which come in a variety of forms, such as fixed deposits, recurring deposits, current deposits, savings accounts, and home safe deposits, enable investors to earn moderate returns on their investments while taking on the least amount of risk [27].

Deposit franchise permits banks to pay deposit rates that are less and insensitive to market interest rates. Banks must generate income that is also insensitive in order to hedge the deposit franchise, which means making long-term fixed-rate loans. According to the study's predictions, banks closely match the sensitivity of their interest income and expense to interest rate changes, protecting their equity from interest rate shocks. Our findings help to clarify why banks offer long-term credit [28].

VII. RISK AND RETURNS OF THE INVESTORS

When it comes to investing in bank products, such as savings accounts, certificates of deposit (CDs), or mutual funds, there are certain risk and return aspects that investors should consider. Here's an explanation of these factors:

7.1 Risk:

a. Credit Risk:

There is always a risk that the bank may default on its financial obligations. If the bank becomes insolvent or fails, investors may face a loss of their invested capital. However, bank deposits are typically insured up to a certain amount by government-backed deposit insurance programs, which provide some protection to individual depositors.

b. Market Risk:

Investments in bank products are subject to market fluctuations and economic conditions. For example, the value of mutual funds can be influenced by changes in interest rates, stock market performance, or overall market sentiment.

c. Liquidity Risk:

Some bank products may have restrictions on the withdrawal of funds for a specific period. For instance, CDs have fixed terms, and early withdrawal may result in penalties. Lack of liquidity can be a disadvantage if investors require immediate access to their funds [27].

7.2 Return:

a. Interest Income:

Many bank products provide a fixed or variable rate of interest, which can generate income for investors. Savings accounts, money market accounts, and certain mutual funds offer interest earnings, albeit at relatively lower rates compared to riskier investments.

b. Dividends and Capital Gains:

Certain bank investment products, such as mutual funds or exchange-traded funds (ETFs), may distribute dividends or generate capital gains through the buying and selling of securities. These can contribute to the overall return.

c. Principal Protection:

Bank products, especially traditional savings accounts and CDs, often prioritize the preservation of principal. While returns may be modest, the risk of losing the initial investment is generally low [28, 29].

It's important for investors to assess their risk tolerance, investment goals, and time horizon when considering bank products. Typically, bank products are perceived as more conservative and suitable for those seeking stability and capital preservation. However, the returns may not be as high as those offered by riskier investment options, such as stocks or real estate. Therefore, investors should weigh the potential returns against the associated risks before making investment decisions. Consulting with a financial advisor can provide personalized guidance based on individual circumstances.

In the process of making decisions on an individual level, risk and return analysis is highly essential. Investors should be willing to take on more risk if they want to earn a higher return. The banking industry, which is the foundation of the nation's economy, has historically provided investors with favourable returns [29]. The banking industry provides feedback on how well bank management made decisions regarding capital size, asset composition, credit risk, and liquidity risk. The study's findings imply that raising asset quality, improving expense control, raising liquidity, and raising capital levels can all increase the profitability of the banking industry [30]. Investors decrease direct investment and increase their holdings of bank deposits during times of increased macroeconomic risk [31].

Some banks have lower returns on investment than others, and some banks have higher investment fluctuation. The banking sector equity market is volatile. Through portfolio analysis, the investors can determine the investments with the lowest risk and highest return. Thus, maximising returns is aided by an understanding of the investment's risk [32]. The previous study reveals that capital level and return on assets are two important factors that are significantly related to all kinds of efficiencies for private banks. However, other elements like non-performing assets, market share, bank size, including ROAs, and capital level are strongly correlated with the effectiveness of public sector banks. As a result, the risk return analysis is determined by the bank's effectiveness [33]. The performance analyses on particular banking shares show that investing in them carries a high level of risk and yields an extremely poor return [34]. The study, risk, and return investigation can be

used to help the investor select the securities of his choice. Risk return analysis gives information about the risk and return performance of various market avenues. Although it is challenging to recognize a pattern for price movements, efforts have been made applying fundamental analysis and technical analysis [35].

Figure 1: Depicts the Risk – return analysis of banking sector

Source: Author

VIII. SWOT ANALYSIS

The Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) approach, which evolved from the SOFT approach, focuses on protecting the Satisfactory while creating Opportunities, addressing Faults, and thwarting Threats [36]. To further evaluate a person's situation in relation to their competition, the study of SWOT Analysis can also be applied at the individual level. The tool's design took both internal and external factors into account. There are connections between internal "weaknesses" and "strengths." The former denoting a quality of a business or other organisation that gives it an advantage over competitors. That same entity's characteristic that puts it at a competitive disadvantage to its competitors is the latter. Opportunities are features of the external field that the organisation can use to its benefit in relation to external factors. However, "threats" are also realities in the larger environment, which could cause issues for the entity [37]. When Multiple Criteria Decision Support (MCDS) techniques are combined with SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis, the SWOT factors' analytical priorities and comparability are produced. The fundamental framework for analysing operational environments in order to support strategic decision-making is provided by SWOT analysis [38]. This study proposes a method to mitigate both downfalls by using Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA) to define SWOT based on consumer feedback, which generates high-priority SWOT corresponding to the consumers' perception. Through the use of IPA-based SWOT analysis, it is anticipated that a company will be able to build strategic planning effectively because it will be clear which SWOT factors should be upgraded or retained based on the viewpoints of the target audience [39].

Table 2: Depicts the SWOT Analysis on Financial Behaviour of Investors in Banking Sector

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The investors' family status encourages them to invest in banking products in order to raise their standards. Investors' income levels affect how income is allocated based on return and risk analysis. Investors' high savings rates encourage them to purchase banking products. Risk-return analysis-based financial discipline is 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investors may be discouraged from investing in the various banking products available due to a lack of financial literacy. Bank deposits have low returns when compared to other types of investments. There is no exposure to new marketable securities related to the banking industry. Investors' educational levels influence how much

practised by investors and helps with investment. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investing in banking products is considered a secure source of income. Additional income for the family in addition to the salary in the form of dividends from banking stocks, interest on deposits, and other sources 	they invest in banking marketable securities. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The amount of investment decreases as the number of dependents increases.
<p style="text-align: center;">Opportunity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased number of financial products under different sectors of financial institutions. Government subsidies were provided for the investment in specific investment products. Inclusion of Digital Banking Convenience makes investors feel comfortable investing. Developed Customer Services educate investors regarding new forms of investment products. Safety Financial Products and Low-Risk Concepts in the Banking Sector 	<p style="text-align: center;">Threat</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher Interest rates on other financial instruments may discourage investors from investing in banking products. Uncertainty about the future of banking products in the present competitive market <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The inflation rate affects the volume of investments by investors as it affects living standards. Tax rate variation influences an investor's decision to invest in banking products.

Source: Author

IX. FINDINGS

- Investor perceptions are certainly having a strong and significant influence on the financial decisions that investors make, making behavioural finance an important and rapidly developing area of financial decision-making that investors must definitely take into consideration.
- In order to understand why and how people make decisions that appear to be illogical or irrational when they spend, save, invest, and borrow money, behavioural finance combines the twin fields of study of psychology and economics.
- Behavioural finance framework investigates the behavioural traits of investors and attempts to comprehend how these patterns assist investment choices
- In terms of earnings and unpredictability, it may be suggested that SBI is the best investment in the banking sector comparative to stock market.
- In order to protect individuals from investment losses, individual investors need to be aware of their biases.
- Lack of financial literacy puts a financial strain on the individual and his investment options. An investor should first learn enough about the different types of investment options that are available to him before deciding which avenues to invest in. He should expand his investment allocation so that he is connected to least risk.

X. SUGGESTIONS

To meet the long-term investment objectives, a well-diversified investment avenues and proper asset allocation are essential. Companies in the financial sector, such as mutual funds, insurance companies, and investment intermediaries, are responsible for educating individual investors so they can make wise investment decisions that lead to financial gains and a thriving economy. Individual planning to invest with the guidance of behavioural finance helps in the development of a sensible and forward-looking approach. A person with financial knowledge would make sure he had sufficient savings and could make plans for a secure retirement.

XI. CONCLUSION

The study's main focus is on how investors behave when considering various investment opportunities, particularly in banks. According to the study, investors' irrational behaviour has a big impact on the investments they choose. Individuals' savings and investments are extremely important for both economic growth and their own financial security. There are some behavioural factors that could reduce people's propensity to invest and save. Some banks offer higher returns, while others have higher risks. The investor

must integrate a higher return with minimal risk. Investors should constantly pay attention to how different banking securities are performing in terms of risk and return. Even though investors have high incomes, are highly educated, are employed, and are independent, Indian investors are conservative and prefer to take the safe route. The bank can create investment products that will appeal to investors with low risk tolerance. As a result, this study discussed how behaviour of investors will help to identify the best investment opportunities based on risk-return analysis. Certain specific investment products offer investors a number of advantages by providing tax benefits along with returns, for both individuals and society.

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